

EFFECTIVE ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING IN KINDERGARTEN

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the urgent problem of teaching English to preschool children in the process of playing activities based on visualizations. English at the preschool age is an urgent area in the methodology that requires new approaches and non-standard solutions.

Keywords: games, child, English, communication, memory, attention, young

Introduction. Today, knowledge of English, which has become the universal language of communication worldwide, is no longer an advantage, but rather a necessity. It is not surprising that parents want their young children to know this language perfectly. In which cases should you look at kindergartens where all communication is exclusively in English? Unlike games in general, pedagogical play has an essential feature – a clearly defined learning goal and a corresponding pedagogical result, which can be justified, highlighted explicitly, and characterized by an educational and cognitive orientation¹. Your child can learn English in the most ordinary state kindergarten. Most often, classes are held there 2 times a week for 20 minutes and can become a good ground for further acquaintance with the subject when the child gets older. Psychologists have proven that kids have excellent long-term memory, so they can easily remember what they learned in the lesson. Thanks to this feature, young children quickly memorize grammatical constructions, and whole word complexes, and learn poems and songs.

Literature review. Therefore, psychologists and specialists in psychophysical development recommend including English in the kindergarten work program so that it helps to develop voluntary and involuntary memory, imagination, thinking, and attention, and creates conditions for faster communication with strangers. Children need to move a lot. Therefore, be sure to alternate calm and active activities in the lesson. Alternate between English assignments for children and games. Change tasks every 5 minutes. By the way, the lesson should not be longer than 20-30 minutes, the kids will get tired. Warm-ups and handclaps are suitable for games, be sure to use games with the words you are learning. For example, we are learning English and the topic "animals", so put cards (or toys) with the studied animals "in the zoo" — in a prominent place in the room. If you are learning fruits and vegetables, then prepare a basket for the lesson, where you can put everything. Use songs in the lessons. It doesn't matter that you can't sing (oh, you can, that's great!) while reading, you can play some lines of the characters in the form of songs, the children will listen, they like it. Consult with the main teachers about the games that can be played during your lesson. For example, when you go through the theme "colors", you can give out felt-tip pens and pencils to children, and let them immediately draw with the colors they use. Learning English since childhood brings many benefits, including ease of communication in the global community and broader career prospects. Parents play an important role in building the right foundation for their children to

¹.Mixaylenko T.M. Igroviye texnologii kak vid pedagogicheskix texnologiy // Pedagogika : traditsii i innovatsii : materialy Mejdunar. nauch. konf. (g. Chelyabinsk, oktyabr' 2011 g.). – T. I. – Chelyabinsk : Dva komsomoltsa, 2011. – S. 140–146.

learn English. Parental support and proper teaching methods contribute to the successful development of the English language and open up a world of new opportunities for the child.

Discussion. Teaching methodology is a set of methods, techniques, technologies, and ways of learning a language. As a rule, this is a clear algorithm of actions that will allow you to learn English from scratch to an advanced level. However, a child under the age of 5 learns words automatically and does not yet understand the rules. Therefore, it is recommended that kids get acquainted with the alphabet, colors, names of toys, fruits, etc. in a playful way. It is better to leave a more thorough education until school age. G.K. Selevko defines the concept of "game technology" as "a type of activity in situations that are aimed at recreating and assimilating social experience, in which self-management of behavior is improved and developed"²

The main goal is to encourage the child to learn the language on his own. As a rule, a separate room is designed for this purpose, where pictures, books, cubes, musical toys, etc., which may arouse the child's interest, are placed. The preschool teaching strategy encourages the child's creative development by telling stories, creating art from available materials, taking walks, and doing fun activities. According to D.B. Elkonin, play is the main activity for preschool children.³ The best methods of education at preschools often involve a combination of play-based learning, hands-on activities, and social interaction. Play-based learning allows children to explore, experiment, and develop their creativity, while hands-on activities help them build fine motor skills and understand concepts through experience. Social interaction, such as group activities and cooperative play, helps children develop important social and emotional skills. Additionally, incorporating music, art, and outdoor play can further enrich the learning experience for preschoolers. In the process of learning English playfully, the teacher can use any opportunity: drawing, playing with dolls and soldiers, modeling from plasticine, active outdoor games. It is not necessary to buy cards with any pictures and words, they can be made independently with the child. To have a fun English lesson, use various card games. For example:

"Steam train" — mix the cards with letters on the table or the floor and ask the child to arrange them in the correct sequence.

"Find neighbors" — shuffle the letter cards and ask the child to choose any of them. The student's task is to find two adjacent letters that go before and after the selected one in the alphabet.

"Path" — the cards are laid out in a path that a young polyglot will follow, his task is to name the depicted pictures, symbols, or figures in English.

The learning process is similar to mastering native speech. Gradually, the child should learn auditory perception of speech, repetition of sounds and words for parents, and reading books if possible. It is noteworthy, but you can even just view the pictures in the book, gradually switching to reading. Then you can gradually connect auxiliary methods. Six original ways to learn English with a child:

Watching cartoons.

Since a year ago, and sometimes even earlier, the child enjoys watching cartoons, and therefore you can turn them on to him, but in English. It doesn't matter that even if you don't

² Selevko G.K. Sovremenniy obrazovatelnyye tekhnologii// Entsiklopediya obrazovatelnykh tekhnologiy : v 2-x t. – T. 1. – M. : Narodnoye obrazovaniye, 2005.

³ Elkonin D.B. Psixologiya igri. – M. : Pedagogika, 1976. – 304 s.

understand much, the child has an advantage over you — linguistic intuition. He can compare words with actions, emotions, and intonations, and draw fairly accurate conclusions about the meaning of words. Often, after watching cartoons in English, the baby begins to pronounce English words. Over time, he will be happy to sing English songs and tell short poems. Now it will be possible to connect the following method. Young children have a well-developed linguistic intuition, and if an unfamiliar word sounds in the video, the child will be able to understand the meaning from the context. There are plenty of educational cartoons in English: Happy Rhymes, Pingu loves English, Tiny Love, etc.

Reproduction of words and phrases.

This method should not resemble the school lessons you know, the point here is different: to communicate with a child using words from the English lexicon in speech, as if by accident. At the same time, foreign words must be appropriate in a specific situation: you cannot talk about animals at breakfast, but the pronunciation of a spoon, fork, plate, milk, etc. in English will be the right decision. It is good if the words are illustrated with appropriate objects. For example, stroking a cat, you can pronounce the word "cat", and learn the word "dog" by putting a stuffed dog next to the child. Gradually, the vocabulary can be expanded by showing the child objects from his everyday environment and voicing their names in Russian and English.

Another way is the "Total Physical Response Method". The physical method or Learning through execution.

The technique is based on physical reactions - it is an approach that follows the idea of "learning by doing". Children will learn English through a series of repetitive actions such as standing up, opening their book, closing the door, and walking to the window and opening it. In this technique, the most important skill is auditory perception, and everything else is secondary and is output through audio perception.

Learning rhymes and songs.

The child will be happy to listen to rhymes and children's songs if combined with staging. For this purpose, play dolls are ideal, with which you can depict a scene from a poem. The main task here is to interest the baby.

Learning games.

There are special games with which you can teach your child English. It would be good to take into account the personal qualities of children — some will like outdoor games, while others will be happy to look at cards with sets of words.

Conclusion. Thus, gaming technologies play an important role in the educational process. The game not only activates the activity of students and reveals cognitive interest, but also trains memory, helps to develop speech skills; stimulates mental activity, develops attention and cognitive interest in the subject. The game is considered one of the methods of overcoming the passivity of students.

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